

THE EFFECT OF CELERY LEAF EXTRACT (*APIUM GRAVEOLENS L.*) ON TNF-A, IL-6 AND MDA LEVELS IN HYPERPIGMENTED WISTAR RATS (*RATTUS NOVERGIUS SP.*)

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Abstract

The objective of this study was to evaluate the anti-inflammatory effects of Celery leaf extract (*Apium graveolens L.*) on hyperpigmented Wistar rats (*Rattus norvegicus sp.*) induced by Azidothymidine (AZT). Celery leaves are known to contain bioactive compounds which may serve as potent anti-inflammatory and antioxidant agents. About 30 male Wistar rats were divided into five groups, including a positive control, a negative control, and groups treated with various doses (1%, 3% and 5%) of celery leaf extract. The study examined inflammation indicators such as MDA, TNF- α , and IL-6. Celery leaf extract significantly ($P < 0.001$) reduced MDA, TNF- α , and IL-6 levels in rats, demonstrating its capacity to attenuate inflammation and oxidative stress produced by AZT. With the increase in celery leaf extract concentration from 1% to 5%, MDA, IL-6 and TNF- α levels decreased from 42.083 ± 3.49 to 28.277 ± 10.27 nmol/ml, 14.588 ± 3.38 to 4.539 ± 1.40 nmol/ml and 667.614 ± 143.41 to 326.920 ± 62.72 nmol/ml respectively. Histopathological examinations demonstrated improvements in skin tissues damaged by inflammation. The results indicate that an ethanol extract of celery leaves has the potential to be an efficient anti-inflammatory drug, notably in lowering AZT-induced inflammation and hyperpigmentation. Further research is required to explore its clinical applicability in controlling inflammatory diseases in human.

Keywords: Celery leaf extract; anti-inflammatory; TNF- α , IL-6; Hyperpigmentation; Azidothymidine.

INTRODUCTION :

The skin is the human body's most layered and heavy organ¹. Hyperpigmentation is a skin condition characterized by an overabundance of pigment. The incidence of hyperpigmentation in Indonesia is relatively high due to Indonesians' skin types, which fall under Fitzpatrick skin phototypes 4 and 5, where the skin rarely burns but constantly darkens. The tropical temperature and high sunlight contribute to the growing prevalence of hyperpigmentation². Hyperpigmentation produces cosmetic concerns that can affect appearance and quality of life, hence mandating prevention and therapy before hyperpigmentation occurs. Genetics, dietary issues, hormones, sunshine, cosmetics, oral medicines, inflammation, cancer, and other factors can all lead to hyperpigmentation³. Melasma, lentigo, post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation, and hyperpigmentation brought on by chemical and pharmaceutical side effects are the four categories of hyperpigmentation problems. Kadek et al⁴ found that 40.7% of 167 patients who had skin tests showed hyperpigmentation, with 62.3% of these cases occurring in women between the ages of 13 and 60. This condition is frequently brought on by using chemical-containing cosmetics for three months to eleven years. In addition, 10% of cases of hyperpigmentation in men and over 40% of women over 30 are particularly sensitive to it. Inflammation is the body's defensive reaction to either tissue damage, foreign object invasion, or both. Microorganisms, mechanical stress, chemical agents, and physical factors are all potential sources of inflammation. Chemical or physical stimuli that induce damage generate the release of inflammatory mediators such as serotonin, histamine, bradykinin, prostaglandins, and others, resulting in redness, heat, discomfort, swelling,

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and more. An increase in vascular permeability, an increase in protein denaturation, and modifications to membranes are all components of inflammation, a process that is frequently linked to pain⁵. Additionally, inflammation is a defensive reaction meant to remove the primary source of the injury-induced necrotic tissue and cell damage. Inflammation is the body's initial immune response to infection, and it varies depending on the type of injury or infection⁶. When healing elements enter injured tissue, inflammation facilitates their removal from the bloodstream. Blood arteries dilate, increasing blood flow to the affected area. Swelling, redness, heat, and discomfort are caused by inflammation because it changes the structure of blood vessels, which makes it easier for blood to reach the tissue⁵. Post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation is defined as brown patches on the skin that have been injured or inflamed, and the spots are large in size but irregular in shape. A complicated vascular tissue's biological reaction to damaging stimuli like infections, irritants, or cell damage is inflammation. In order to reduce the discomfort brought on by the inflammatory process, a drug that addresses inflammation is therefore necessary⁶. Azidothymidine (AZT) can induce hyperpigmentation in the skin by increasing melanin levels⁷. Azidothymidine, also known as zidovudine, has been suggested as the first antiretroviral medication for the treatment of HIV-1. It is one of the substances that effectively inhibits the DNA polymerase activity of the HIV-1 RT (Reverse Transcriptase) enzyme. In order to combat HIV-1, combination medicines now include RT inhibitors as a crucial component⁸. The first antiviral drug authorized for the treatment of the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) was azidothymidine (AZT)⁷.

The invasion of blood monocytes and the activation of tissue macrophages are the outcomes of nearly all inflammatory events. The cytokines TNF, IL-1, and IL-6 are produced as a result of this activity, and these cytokines have a variety of effects on the host, including the induction of fever, the hepatic acute-phase response followed by leucocytosis, the production of acute-phase proteins like C-Reactive Protein (CRP), and the differentiation of T cells, B cells, and macrophages⁹. Interleukin 6 (IL-6) may function as a marker of significant inflammation in COVID-19 patients with a bad prognosis¹⁰. Interleukin 6 (IL-6) functions as both an anti-inflammatory cytokine and an anti-inflammatory myokine¹⁰. It is encoded by the IL-6 gene in humans. Moreover, osteoblasts release IL-6 to promote the development of osteoclasts. Many bloods vascular stroma's smooth muscle cells also generate the pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-6. The fact that IL-6 inhibits TNF- α and IL-1, as well as activating IL-1ra and IL-10, demonstrates its function as an anti-inflammatory myokine¹⁰. In other hand, Malondialdehyde (MDA) is a reactive dialdehyde molecule formed in vivo as a result of lipid peroxidation, either enzymatically or non-enzymatically that is produced as a byproduct of lipid peroxidation and is one of several reactive electrophilic molecules that put cells under hazardous stress¹¹. Elevated MDA values signify membrane oxidation. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) have been examined in eczema and other skin diseases, but their significance in atopic dermatitis (AD) has received less attention. Mutagenic compounds can be created when MDA combines with deoxyguanosine and deoxyadenosine in DNA¹². Thus, malondialdehyde is an excellent biomarker for oxidative stress^{13,14}. TNF- α contributes to systemic inflammation at moderate levels and can produce pathological abnormalities like septic shock at high levels¹⁵. This is related to the cytotoxic nature of TNF- α (Tumour Necrosis Factor alpha). TNF- α contributes to host defence against bacterial, parasite, and viral illnesses¹⁵. Macrophages create TNF- α , which is then triggered by antigens, T lymphocytes, NK cells, and mast cells^{15,16}. In healthy persons, TNF- α is typically undetectable; nevertheless, it is frequently discovered in the serum when inflammatory and infectious diseases are present. TNF- α , a powerful pyrogen, affects leukocytes and endothelial cells, causing acute inflammation even at low levels¹⁶.

Celery is widely used as a vegetable or as a side dish, and it is increasingly being utilized as a medication¹⁷. Organic chemicals found in celery leaves include flavonoids, tannins, saponins, flavo-glycosides (apiin), and apigenin. Celery, according to Yongkhamcha¹⁸, also has a number of bioactive components. Using diclofenac as a comparison, Sapri¹⁹ reports that celery leaf water extract exhibits anti-inflammatory efficacy in male mice induced with carrageenan. Numerous investigations have been carried out on naturally occurring anti-inflammatory substances, including fruit peels²⁰, rambutan leaves²¹, and Sesewanua plants²². On the other hand, the benefits of celery leaf extract on hyperpigmentation have not yet been studied. Therefore, this study aims to examine the impact of Azidothymidine-induced hyperpigmentation in Wistar rats (*Rattus norvegicus Sp*) on the anti-inflammatory activity of celery leaf extract (*Apium graveolens L.*).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Hyperpigmentation and Post-Inflammatory Hyperpigmentation (PIH)

The skin is the largest and most layered organ in the body, serving as the body's primary barrier to the environment. One common skin problem is hyperpigmentation, a condition characterized by increased melanin production/accumulation that causes darkening of certain skin areas (1). In Indonesia, the prevalence of hyperpigmentation is relatively high because the majority of people have Fitzpatrick IV–V skin types, which tend to darken easily, coupled with high year-round exposure to ultraviolet light in tropical climates (2). The triggers for

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hyperpigmentation are diverse, including genetics, hormones, sun exposure, cosmetics, oral medications, inflammation, and certain pathological conditions (3). Clinically, hyperpigmentation can appear as melasma, lentigo, PIH, or hyperpigmentation due to side effects of chemicals/pharmaceuticals (3). Clinical evidence in Indonesia shows that hyperpigmentation is common, especially in the productive age group and is often associated with long-term use of cosmetics containing certain ingredients (4). In PIH, the inflammatory process in the skin is key because inflammatory mediators and oxidative stress can increase melanogenesis activity or alter melanosome distribution, resulting in dark patches remaining after the inflammation subsides (27).

Skin Inflammation: Mediators, Cytokines, and Its Relationship to Melanogenesis

Inflammation is the body's protective response to tissue injury or invasion by foreign agents, involving vasodilation, increased vascular permeability, leukocyte migration, and the release of chemical mediators (5,6). In the skin, inflammation can be triggered by allergens, infections, chemical stimuli, or physical trauma, and is histologically characterized by microvascular changes and immune cell recruitment (27). Mediators such as histamine, serotonin, prostaglandins, bradykinin, and kinins promote the classic symptoms of inflammation (rubor, calor, tumor, dolor, and functio laesa) (5,6). Inflammation is also directly linked to pigmentation changes. Recent reviews emphasize that inflammatory factors may play a role in melanogenesis through cytokine and cellular signaling pathways that influence tyrosinase activity and melanocyte function (27). The interaction between proinflammatory cytokines and skin cells (keratinocytes, fibroblasts, melanocytes) can increase or suppress melanin production depending on the context and the dominance of the activated pathways (27,28).

TNF- α and IL-6 as Biomarkers of Systemic and Local Inflammation

TNF- α is a central proinflammatory cytokine primarily produced by macrophages and other immune cells following antigen/infection stimulation and plays a role in acute inflammation through leukocyte and endothelial activation (15,16). Under physiological conditions, TNF- α is typically very low or barely detectable, but increases in inflammatory and infectious states (15,16). TNF- α also has broad effects, ranging from fever induction to contributing to tissue damage when excessive (15). IL-6 is a pleiotropic cytokine involved in inflammation, immunity, hematopoiesis, and the acute-phase response; in various conditions, it is often used as a marker of severe inflammation and prognosis (11). In the context of skin, IL-6 and TNF- α can influence melanogenesis directly and indirectly through the regulation of inflammatory signals that modulate melanocyte/tyrosinase activity (27,28). Thus, TNF- α and IL-6 are relevant as indicators of inflammatory changes that potentially contribute to post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation.

Oxidative Stress and Malondialdehyde (MDA) in Skin Disease

Oxidative stress occurs when the production of oxidants (e.g., ROS) exceeds the capacity of the antioxidant system. In skin, ROS can exacerbate inflammation, damage cell membranes, and trigger signaling changes related to pigmentation (11,12). Malondialdehyde (MDA) is an end product of lipid peroxidation that is often used as a stable biomarker to assess the degree of oxidative membrane damage (12,13). Elevated MDA reflects increased lipid oxidation and may contribute to cellular stress; MDA can even react with DNA to form mutagenic adducts (12,13). Studies in inflammatory skin conditions have also shown that MDA increases with the degree of inflammation (28), making MDA measurement relevant for assessing the inflammatory–oxidative relationship in drug-induced hyperpigmentation models.

Azidothymidine (AZT/Zidovudine) sebagai Induktor Hiperpigmentasi dan Inflamasi

Azidothymidine (AZT) atau zidovudine adalah antiretroviral golongan nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitor (NRTI) yang merupakan salah satu obat awal untuk terapi HIV (7,8). Selain manfaat klinisnya, AZT dilaporkan dapat menimbulkan efek samping, termasuk perubahan pigmentasi kulit (7). Secara biologis, efek AZT juga dikaitkan dengan mediator inflamasi, stres oksidatif, dan stres retikulum endoplasma dalam konteks akumulasi lipid hepatic dan inflamasi sistemik (10). Karena itu, AZT relevan digunakan sebagai agen induksi pada model hewan untuk menilai keterkaitan inflamasi—stres oksidatif—perubahan pigmentasi dan efektivitas kandidat antiinflamasi/antioksidan.

Celery (*Apium graveolens L.*) as a Source of Anti-Inflammatory and Antioxidant Bioactive Compounds

Celery (*Apium graveolens L.*) is widely known as a vegetable and medicinal plant. Its leaves contain various bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, tannins, saponins, glycosides (apiin), and apigenin, which have the potential to provide antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects (17). Several preclinical studies have shown celery extract to

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have anti-inflammatory activity, for example in a carrageenan-induced inflammation model compared to standard drugs (19). In addition to celery, research trends also indicate that many natural products (fruit peels, certain plant leaves) are being studied as anti-inflammatory candidates (20–22), strengthening the rationale for selecting medicinal plants as adjunct therapies. From a mechanistic perspective, polyphenol/flavonoid compounds from plants can suppress the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines by modulating the NF- κ B and MAPK pathways, which are key regulators of inflammatory mediator expression (31,32). Studies of polyphenol-rich fractions from celery leaves have shown potential to suppress NF- κ B and MAPK signaling, thereby reducing the inflammatory response (32). Furthermore, several components frequently associated with anti-inflammatory/skin-related biological effects include kojic acid (with evidence in LPS-exposed keratinocytes) (29), gallic acid (30), and stachydrine, which can suppress the NF- κ B/MAPK pathway in inflammatory models (31). This literature supports the hypothesis that celery leaf extract can reduce TNF- α , IL-6, and oxidative stress markers such as MDA.

Research Gaps and Current State of the Study

Although the anti-inflammatory activity of celery has been extensively studied in several inflammatory models (19, 32), studies specifically linking celery leaf extract to AZT-induced hyperpigmentation and key biological parameters (TNF- α , IL-6, MDA) are limited. Considering that hyperpigmentation (especially PIH) is closely related to inflammation and oxidative stress (12,27,28), evaluation of celery leaf extract in drug-induced hyperpigmentation models is relevant to fill this gap—both for mechanistic understanding and the potential development of natural product-based anti-inflammatory/antioxidant candidates.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials

The material used in this study is celery leaves (*Apium graveolens L.*) grown in Medan, Indonesia. All other chemicals were of analytical grade purchased from local suppliers.

Study Design and Subject:

The study's test animals were male Wistar white rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) that were 2-3 months old, weighed about 150-200 grams, and were in good health. The research subjects were divided into five groups, each consisting of six male Wistar white rats. The celery leaf extract was given at 1%, 3% and 5% for 21 days. The effect of the celery extract on the sample was analysed every 2 days from 0 day until day 21. The following were the groups as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Group of Sample Criteria

Group	Kode	Criteria
Group 1	Control	Control Group, which was provided with food and water in its cage as usual and received no other care
Group 2	K2SA	Positive Control, AZT 600 mg/kg body weight was given with a suspension of Salicylic Acid 45 mg/kg body weight
Group 3	K3S1%	AZT 55 mg/kg body weight, test suspension of celery leaf ethanol extract at 1%
Group 4	K4S3%	AZT 55 mg/kg body weight, test suspension of celery leaf ethanol extract at 3%
Group 5	K5S5%	AZT 55 mg/kg body weight, test suspension of celery leaf ethanol extract at 5%

Celery leaf extraction

The obtained plant material was allowed to dry completely at a temperature of 24–26 °C. Celery leaf extraction was prepared followed method by AOAC method²³, celery leaves were extracted through maceration with 96% ethanol. Ten simplicial portions should be placed in a dark container. Pour 75 parts 96% ethanol, cover, and leave for 5 days, sheltered from light, stirring frequently. Squeeze, strain, and wash the residue with enough solvent to yield 100 parts. After transferring the mixture to a closed container, store it for two days in a cool, dry location. Pour off the clear liquid without disturbing the sediment. Using a rotary evaporator set at $\pm 40^{\circ}\text{C}$, the macerate is evaporated until a thick extract is produced. The ethanol-free extract was lyophilized and stored in a dark environment until it was needed.

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Preparation of 0.5% Na CMC suspension

After evenly dispersing 0.5 g of Natrium Carboxymethyl Cellulose (Na CMC) into a mortar with 10 ml of distilled water (70°C), the mixture was covered and allowed to sit for 15 minutes until a translucent mass was formed. Then, it was powdered and made up to a 100 ml volume by diluting it with distilled water.

Preparation of ethanolic celery leaf extract suspension

Celery leaf ethanol extract (1%, 3%, and 5%) was then combined with 10 milliliters of 0.5% Na CMC solution.

Preparation of Salicylic acid suspension, Azidothymidine

Salicylic suspension was prepared by weighing 58.60 mg of salicylic acid powder and homogeneously crushed with 0.5% Na CMC suspension. It was then transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask and filled to capacity with 0.5% Na CMC suspension. In order to prepare Azidothymidine (AZT), grind 50 mg of Azidothymidine until homogenous with 0.9% NaCl solution, then transfer to a 5 ml volumetric flask and fill to the mark with 0.9% NaCl solution. The combination was incubated for twenty-four hours at 37°C.

Measurement of Malondialdehyde (MDA)

Measurement of MDA followed method by Lauro et al¹¹. A mortar was used to grind quartz sand and 0.5 grams of rat kidney tissue until it was smooth. Next, the mortar was filled with 200 μ L of physiological NaCl. Following the homogenate's transfer, 550 μ L of distilled water was put in a polypropylene tube. Next, 100 μ L of TCA was added and homogenized. Then, 250 μ L of 1N HCl was added and homogenized. The mixture was then added with 100 μ L of 1% Na-Thio and centrifuged at 500 rpm for 10 minutes. Glass wool was used to collect and filter the supernatant. The obtained supernatant was boiled in a water bath at 100 °C for 20 minutes. The heated supernatant was then allowed to cool to room temperature.

Measurement of Interleukin 6 (IL-6) & Tumour Necrosis Factor alpha (TNF- α)

Measurement of IL-6 followed method by Nordan et al²⁴ using ELISA kit. Furthermore, measurement of TNF- α was done followed method by Valaperti et al²⁵. The kit instructions were followed to ensure that the levels of TNF- α and Interleukin-6 were measured in male white rats. Male white rats from each treatment group had their serum levels of TNF- α and IL-6 measured, and the results were compared to the measurements in the control group

Detection of Bioactive compound by GC-MS Analysis

GC-MS analysis was done followed method Sun et al²⁶, by A 99.999% pure helium carrier gas was used to inject an extracted sample into the apparatus at a forward purge flow rate of 3 mL/min and a continuous over-column gas flow rate of 1 mL/min. The isothermal splitless mode of the Agilent DB-WAX (30 m 250 m 0.25 m, Agilent Technologies Inc., Santa Clara, CA, USA) column was utilized for the separation of volatile organic compounds. Starting at 50 C, the temperature of the GC column was raised by 6 C in 1 minute, ramping up to 230 C, and then maintained for 5 min. The quadrupole mass detector, ion source, and transmission line were set to 250, 230, and 150 C, respectively, of temperature. With an electron impact mode of 70 eV and a mass spectrometer scan range of (Mass/Charge Ratio) m/z 20 to 550 amu, MS detection was accomplished. An ionization energy of 70 eV was recorded using the electron ionization-mass spectrometry (EI-MS) technique. There was no delay in the solvent.

Statistical Analysis

The mean standard deviations of three parallel measurements are represented by the data shown in tables and figures. Based on the Duncan's multiple range test, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was utilized to examine any variations between the means for various extracts. A significance level of 5% ($p = 0.05$) was used in this investigation to make a statistical test decision. There will be a post hoc Sheffe test if the p -value < 0.05. There will be a Levene's test if the p -value is greater than 0.05. Version 19 of SPSS Statistics (IBM SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) was used to test the data, and differences at $p < 0.05$ were deemed significant.

RESULT:

MDA, IL-6 and TNF- α concentration in hyperpigmented Wistar rats (*Rattus Novergicus Sp.*) induced by Azidothymidine

After 21 days of treatment with celery leaf extract, the MDA level was determined using the ELISA method. According to Table 2, the MDA level was determined in sample K3S1%, K4S3% and K5S5% were 42.083 ± 3.49

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nmol/ml, 37.032 ± 10.86 nmol/ml and 28.277 ± 10.27 nmol/ml respectively. IL-6 was the inflammatory mediator evaluated in this investigation. According to Table 2, K2SA had the highest IL-6 (17.193 ± 1.87), while the control group (0.433 ± 0.26), which did not receive any therapy and was merely given food and water in its cage, had the lowest value. The ELISA method was used to measure the TNF- α level, and observations were also conducted. Table 2 shows that the control group had the highest TNF- α level, 281.621 ± 14.76 , whereas sample K2SA had the lowest TNF- α level, 778.589 ± 80.43 .

Table 2. MDA, IL-6 and TNF- α concentration in Hyperpigmented Wistar Rats (*Rattus Novergicus Sp.*) Induced by Azidothymidine

Sample	MDA (nmol/ml)	IL-6 (nmol/ml)	TNF- α (nmol/ml)
Control	12.792 ± 2.19^a	0.433 ± 0.26^a	281.621 ± 14.76^a
K2SA	62.29 ± 61.18^e	17.193 ± 1.87^e	778.589 ± 80.43^e
K3S1%	42.08 ± 3.49^d	14.588 ± 3.38^d	667.614 ± 143.40^d
K4S3%	37.032 ± 10.86^c	11.939 ± 3.05^c	452.812 ± 63.68^c
K5S5%	28.277 ± 10.27^b	4.539 ± 1.40^b	326.925 ± 62.72^b

*Control= was provided with food and water in its cage as usual and received no other care; K2SA= Positive Control, AZT 600 mg/kg body weight was given with a suspension of Salicylic Acid 45 mg/kg body weight; K3S1%= AZT 55 mg/kg body weight, test suspension of celery leaf ethanol extract at 1%;K4S3%= AZT 55 mg/kg body weight, test suspension of celery leaf ethanol extract at 3%; K5S5%= AZT 55 mg/kg body weight, test suspension of celery leaf ethanol extract at 5%; MDA= Malondialdehyde; IL-6=Interleukin 6; TNF- α = Tumour Necrosis Factor alpha; Different superscripts letters in the same column indicate differences ($p < 0.05$) amongst the means, as determined by the Duncan’s multiple range test.

Comparative analysis of celery leaf extract’s effect on MDA, IL-6 and TNF- α level in hyperpigmented Wistar rats (*Rattus Novergicus Sp.*) induced by Azidothymidine

The MDA levels in each group of research samples were compared in each group of samples. There was a significant difference ($p < 0.001$) in the MDA levels among all sample groups in Table 3. In order to examine the variations in MDA levels between sample groups with various sample sizes in further detail, a post hoc test was used. Based on the result indicates that there was a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the MDA levels between all sample groups that received the celery leaf extract intervention and the negative control group.

Table 3. Post hoc analysis

Variable	P-value					
	Contro l	K2SA	K3S1 %	K4S3 %	K5S5 %	
MDA	Control	-	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.002
	K2SA	0.001	-	0.001	0.001	0.003
	K3S1%	0.001	0.000	-	0.001	0.002
	K4S3%	0.000	0.000	0.001	-	0.000
	K5S5%	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	-
IL-6	Control	-	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.002
	K2SA	0.001	-	0.001	0.001	0.003
	K3S1%	0.001	0.000	-	0.001	0.002
	K4S3%	0.000	0.000	0.001	-	0.000
	K5S5%	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	-
TNF- α	Control	-	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.002
	K2SA	0.001	-	0.001	0.001	0.003
	K3S1%	0.001	0.000	-	0.001	0.002
	K4S3%	0.000	0.000	0.001	-	0.000
	K5S5%	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	-

*Post Hoc Test Scheffe; Control= was provided with food and water in its cage as usual and received no other care; K2SA= Positive Control, AZT 600 mg/kg body weight was given with a suspension of Salicylic Acid 45 mg/kg body weight; K3S1%= AZT 55 mg/kg body weight, test suspension of celery leaf ethanol extract at 1%;K4S3%= AZT 55 mg/kg body weight, test suspension of celery leaf ethanol extract at 3%; K5S5%= AZT 55 mg/kg body weight, test suspension of celery leaf ethanol extract at 5%; MDA= Malondialdehyde; IL-6=Interleukin 6; TNF- α = Tumour Necrosis Factor alpha

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Table 3 shows a significant difference in IL-6 and TNF- α levels across all sample groups ($p < 0.001$). The results demonstrated a significant difference in IL-6 and TNF- α levels between the negative control group and sample groups that received the celery leaf extract intervention ($p < 0.05$).

GC-MS profile

The results of GCMS-based bioactive component screening in celery leaf extract are displayed in Table 4. Based on the results, the compounds with bioactivity, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and skin-brightening properties, detected in the celery leaf extract are (-)-threo-isodihomocitric acid (C₈H₁₂O₇), Limonin (C₂₆H₃₀O₈), 5-Hydroxy-2-furoic acid (C₅H₄O₄), gamma-Aminobutyric acid (C₄H₉NO₂), Kojic acid (C₆H₆O₄), tranexamic acid (C₈H₁₅NO₂), alpha-Ketoglutaric acid (C₅H₆O₅). Furthermore, most compounds showed modest delta mass values, such as 5-Hydroxy-2-furoic acid with a delta mass of -0.25 ppm and Kojic acid with a delta mass of -126 ppm, showing that the measurements were precise and in line with theoretical values.

Table 4. GC-MS Profile

No	Name	Formula	Annot. DeltaMass [ppm]	Calc. MW	RT [min]	Sample Area
1	(-)-threo-isodihomocitric acid	C ₈ H ₁₂ O ₇	-1,44	220,05799	4,277	33623420,96
2	4-Aminobenzoic acid	C ₇ H ₇ N O ₂	0,16	137,0477	1,081	33901483,52
3	.alpha.-Aminoadipic acid	C ₆ H ₁₁ N O ₄	-0,78	161,06868	1,118	33945202,07
4	N-glycoloyl-D-mannosaminolactone	C ₈ H ₁₃ N O ₇	-0,85	235,069	1,102	34211841,12
5	5-Hydroxy-2-furoic acid	C ₅ H ₄ O ₄	-0,25	128,01093	2,003	34801207,28
6	trans-Aconitic acid	C ₆ H ₆ O ₆	-0,63	174,01633	1,418	35237650,38
7	N-[4-(diethylamino)phenyl]-N'-phenylurea	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₃ O	77617,62	305,14733	1,06	37516285,52
8	L-Pyrogutamic acid	C ₅ H ₇ N O ₃	-0,39	129,04254	1,14	41913515,49
9	Butyryl dihydrogen phosphate	C ₄ H ₉ O ₅ P	-2,48	168,01834	1,887	42422693,21
10	1-[(3-Carboxypropyl)amino]-1-deoxy-beta-D-fructofuranose	C ₁₀ H ₁₉ N O ₇	-0,86	265,11592	4,844	42559852,14
11	D-(+)-Pyrogutamic Acid	C ₅ H ₇ N O ₃	-0,39	129,04254	1,409	43130774,53
12	DL-Arginine	C ₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂	-0,93	174,11151	1,024	45610132,54
13	Kojic acid	C ₆ H ₆ O ₄	-1,26	142,02643	4,847	47046391,63
14	N-[(4E)-1-(Hexopyranosyloxy)-3-hydroxy-4-octadecen-2-yl]-2-hydroxyhexadecanamide	C ₄₀ H ₇₇ N O ₉	-0,39	715,55956	29,254	48867626,56
15	2-Methoxy-4-[3,5,6-trihydroxy-7-(sulfinooxy)-3,4-dihydro-2H-chromen-2-yl]phenyl hydrogen sulfate	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₁₂ S ₂	1,97	464,00923	2,015	52196337,48
16	2-Amino-1,3,4-octadecanetriol	C ₁₈ H ₃₉ N O ₃	-2,62	317,29216	17,393	53867903,58
17	alpha-Ketoglutaric acid	C ₅ H ₆ O ₅	-1,09	146,02136	1,41	54029380,32
18	N-[(4E)-1-(Hexopyranosyloxy)-3-hydroxy-4-octadecen-2-yl]-2-hydroxyhexadecanamide	C ₄₀ H ₇₇ N O ₉	-0,39	715,55956	28,565	55348557,66
19	L-(+)-Valine	C ₅ H ₁₁ N O ₂	0,94	117,07909	1,125	59095147,5
20	tranexamic acid	C ₈ H ₁₅ N O ₂	-1,18	157,11009	1,414	60039163,46
21	gamma-Aminobutyric acid	C ₄ H ₉ N O ₂	1,82	103,06352	1,049	60416830,43
22	5-methyl-4-[[[(2S,3R,4S,5S,6R)-3,4,5-trihydroxy-6-(hydroxymethyl)oxan-2-yl]oxy]-2H-chromen-2-one	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₈	112279,11	376,06175	1,174	62537173,29
23	O-ureido-D-serine	C ₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₄	0,7	163,05942	0,939	65692968,34
24	5-Hydroxy-2-furoic acid	C ₅ H ₄ O ₄	-0,25	128,01093	1,409	65762741,67
25	Limonin	C ₂₆ H ₃₀ O ₈	-1,86	470,19319	14,78	67219585,41
26	(-)-threo-isodihomocitric acid	C ₈ H ₁₂ O ₇	-1,44	220,05799	4,845	72988774,81

*RT = Retention time; MW = molecular weight

DISCUSSION:

The purpose of this study was to investigate the effect of celery leaf extract (*Apium graveolens L.*) on inflammation in hyperpigmented Wistar rats (*Rattus norvegicus Sp*) produced by Azidothymidine. Inflammation is a local defensive reaction triggered by trauma or tissue damage that seeks to remove or reduce dangerous agents or damaged tissues. Pain, heat (calor), redness (rubor), swelling (tumor), and loss of function (functio laesa) are the

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symptoms of inflammation in its acute phase. Allergens, infections, chemical stimuli, and physical injury, according to Chuhan²⁷, can produce skin inflammation in response to external or endogenous stimuli. Through its ability to combat bacterial invasion and other pathogens and to promote wound healing, skin inflammation plays a vital role in the body. Histologically, it is characterized by a complicated set of processes, including artery, capillary, and venule dilatation, enhanced blood flow permeability, exudation of plasma proteins, and leukocyte recruitment to the inflammation site. The release of mediators (histamine, serotonin, prostaglandins, and kinins) regulates and activates blood and tissue cells, causing this response and potentially resulting in tissue damage symptoms. The metabolism of arachidonic acid, an unsaturated fatty acid containing 20 carbon atoms, leads to inflammation.

Azidothymidine (AZT or zidovudine) is a chemical that inhibits the DNA polymerase activity of the HIV-1 RT (Reverse Transcriptase) enzyme and has been suggested as the first antiretroviral medication for HIV-1 treatment⁷. The first antiviral medication authorized for the treatment of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) was azidothymidine (AZT). MDA levels were determined using the ELISA technique following 21 days of celery leaf extract treatment. Control sample had the lowest MDA level (12.792 ± 2.19 nmol/ml), while sample K2SA had the highest (62.296 ± 61.18 nmol/ml) MDA level. This is similar with Kodariah's²⁸ finding that celery extract lowered MDA levels in rat plasma and possibly minimize oxidative stress. Oxidative stress is brought on by an imbalance between oxidants and antioxidants, with oxidants predominating. Compared to other aldehydes, MDA, a byproduct of lipid peroxidation, is more mutagenic²⁹. MDA is frequently employed as a measure of oxidative stress since it is chemically stable.

A pathological process known as inflammation is the body's protective response to damaging stimuli through vascular reactions in living tissue. The chemical components involved in mediating inflammatory reactions are called inflammatory mediators or chemical mediators. Th cells, lymphocytes, macrophages, monocytes, and other related cells release inflammatory mediators. Th1 cells secrete cytokines such as IL-2, IL-3, and tumor necrosis factor (TNF), which are essential components of cellular immune responses²⁸. Th2 cells secrete IL-4, IL-5, IL-10, IL-13, IL-3, and other cytokines, which are critical for humoral immune responses³⁰. Certain disorders cause a disruption in the equilibrium between Th1 and Th2, which leads to a shift toward either Th1 or Th2. Helper T cells 17 (Th17) are a subpopulation of T cells that release IL-6 and participate in innate immunity and inflammation by secreting IL-7, IL-6, and TNF- α . Melanocytes can release TNF- α , however fibroblasts can only secrete TNF and IL-6. Different skin cell types release inflammatory mediators.

TNF- α levels were evaluated using the ELISA technique following 21 days of celery leaf extract treatment. Sample K2SA had the highest TNF- α level (775.581 ± 80.43 nmol/ml), while K3S1% had the highest TNF- α level among the sample with celery leaf extract treatment (667.614 ± 143.41 nmol/ml). TNF- α levels were shown to decrease when celery leaf extract dosage was increased. Celery leaf extract containing Kojic acid, gallic acid, and DL-Stachydrine demonstrated potential as anti-inflammatory drugs by lowering TNF- α levels, especially in endothelium and cardiac cell-related inflammation^{30,31,32}. Th1, Th17, Th22, monocytes, macrophages, keratinocytes, dendritic cells, and two different receptors are the sources of this homotrimer cytokine, known as TNF. TNF not only causes inflammation via immune cells and vascular endothelial cells, but it also controls apoptosis, which in turn controls the growth of lymphoid tissues²⁸. According to Chuhan²⁸, TNF inhibition can quickly restore the expression of genes related to pigmentation. Furthermore, IL and TNF together have the ability to suppress melanogenesis. Thus, increasing the dosage of celery leaf extract will decrease TNF levels, which can lessen hyperpigmentation.

Interleukin (IL-6) is able to control melanogenesis and the proliferation and differentiation of epidermal melanocytes both directly and indirectly²⁸. By controlling cell proliferation, survival, and differentiation, IL-6 is released by keratinocytes, epidermal cells, fibroblasts, and dermal endothelial cells. It is implicated in immunological responses, inflammation, haematopoiesis, and cancer. Tyrosinase activity and melanogenesis can both be decreased by IL-6²⁸. The study found that K3S1% had the highest IL-6 level among the celery leaf extract groups, at 14.588 ± 3.384 nmol/ml. The levels of IL-6 decrease with increasing celery leaf extract concentration. Numerous bioactive substances with anti-inflammatory properties found in celery leaf extract have the ability to inhibit the synthesis of pro-inflammatory cytokines like IL-6. These bioactive substances lessen oxidative stress and prevent the NF- κ B pathway—the main controller of cytokine production—from being activated^{30,33}.

This investigation supports Hostetler et al.'s³⁴ discovery that celery leaf extract can reduce and avoid inflammation and gastrointestinal irritation. Phototoxic chemicals found in a variety of plants, such as citrus fruits, celery, carrots, and figs, can cause phototoxic reactions³⁵. Hyperpigmentation may arise due to increased melanosomes. Celery extract contains luteolin, ferulic acid, and caffeic acid in addition to being a strong source of polyphenol antioxidants³⁴. These substances are able to counteract the harm that free radical reactions cause. Celery extract can be utilized as a cosmetic ingredient at specific concentrations, according to the study's findings.

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(-)-threo-isodihomocitric acid was shown to be the most prevalent chemical in celery leaf extract by GCMS analysis, with limonin and Kojic acid following closely behind. Limonin, 5-hydroxy-2-furoic acid, and gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) are non-polar and more volatile molecules that can be detected by GCMS. This work supports the findings of Naghneh et al³⁵, who discovered that the primary bioactive components in celery extract are phthalides, sesquiterpenes, and monoterpenes, with limonene being the most prevalent monoterpene found in the extract. The bioactive chemicals found in celery leaf extract have the ability to decrease cytokines, including TNF- α and IL-6, which are involved in the induction of chemokines that aid in the recruitment of immune cells to sites of damage and infection. By decreasing the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) by stimulated immune cells and keratinocytes.

CONCLUSION

According to the research findings, male Wistar rats (*Rattus norvegicus sp.*) that were hyperpigmented as a result of Azidothymidine induction showed a reduction in the percentage of inflammation when exposed to an ethanol extract of celery leaves. Following 21 days of celery leaf extract administration, the study demonstrated substantial changes in MDA, TNF- α , and IL-6 levels between the normal group and the positive control group (whether or not treated with celery ethanol extract). The reduction in MDA (malondialdehyde) levels in male Wistar rats experiencing hyperpigmentation from Azidothymidine induction to 28.277 ± 10.27 nmol/ml with increasing concentration of celery leaf extract is indicative of this. Moreover, the reduction in TNF- α levels suggests that celery leaf extract has an impact on inflammatory modulation. TNF- α levels decreased as the concentration of celery leaf extract was increased from 1% to 5%, going from 667.614 ± 143.41 nmol/ml to 326.925 ± 62.72 nmol/ml. Additionally, IL-6 levels were significantly lower in the study, suggesting that celery leaf extract may have anti-inflammatory properties. Celery leaf extract dosage increased from 1% to 5% resulted in a decrease in IL-6 levels from 14.588 ± 3.38 nmol/ml to 4.539 ± 1.40 nmol/ml.

REFERENCES

- Kianmaswati NA, Siti H, Nopi R. Review: Perbandingan Beberapa Ekstrak Kulit buah sebagai Anti-hiperpigmentasi, *Jurnal Sains dan Kesehatan*. 2021; 3(2):335-342.
- Sri Lestari. Cosmeceutical Untuk Hiperpigmentasi, *Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology Update Symposium Proceedings*. 2011.
- Syarif M. Wasitaatmadya, *Dermatologi Kosmetik*, 2nd ed, Faculty of Medical Universitas Indonesia, 2011.
- Ni Kadek S, Indira IGAAE, Ni Made DP. Insiden dan Profil Melasma di Rumah Sakit Umum Pusat Sanglah Denpasar Periode Januari 2014 Sampai Desember 2014. *E-Jurnal Medika*. 2019;8(2):1-7.
- Leelaprakash GS, Mohan D. Invitro Anti-Inflammatory Activity of Methanol Extract of *Enicostemma Axillare*. *International Journal of Drug Development & Research*. 2011;3(3): 189-196.
- Rahmad SS, Ade FT, Aflahun FS. Studi Literatur Tentang Pemanfaatan Tanaman Obat Tradisional. *Seminar of Social Science Engineering & Humaniora, Proceeding*. 2020;385-391.
- Eichinger S, Pabinger I, Hartl H, Stain C, Mayerhofer S, Schweiger C, Kier P, Schwarzingler I, Kyrle PA, Lechner K. Azidothymidine (AZT) in The Treatment of Symptomatic HIV-1-Infected Hemophiliacs. *Thromb Haemost*. 1990;64(1):108-12.
- Robets LJ, Morrow JD. Senyawa analgesik-antipiretik dan Antiradang Serta Obat-obat yang digunakan dalam Penanganan Pirai. *Dasar Farmakologi Terapi*, 10th edition. Bandung: Buku Kedokteran EGC. 666-668. 2012.
- Ivander AS. Profil Tumor Necrosis Factor (TNF α) Berdasarkan Indeks Massa Tubuh (IMT) pada Mahasiswa Fakultas Kedokteran UNSRAT Angkatan 2014. *Jurnal e-Biomedik*. 2015;3(2):640-643.
- Atrayee B, Mohamed AA, Jang S, Byoung-joon Song. Zidovudine (AZT) and Hepatic Lipid Accumulation: Implication of Inflammation, Oxidative and Endoplasmic Reticulum Stress Mediators. *PLOS ONE*. 2013;8(10):1-9.
- Lauro VS, Antonio VR, Luis LR, Manuel VB. The Role of Interleukin 6 During Viral Infections. *Front. Microbiol*, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2019.01057>.
- Ayala A, Muñoz M, Argüelles S. Lipid peroxidation: production, metabolism, and signaling mechanisms of Malondialdehyde and 4-Hydroxy-2-Nonenal. *Oxid Med Cell Longev*. 2014;112:21-8.
- Murray R, Robert K, Darly K, Garner, Victor W, *DNA: Susunan, Replikasi, & Perbaikannya*, 27th Ed. 2009. Jakarta: Egc.

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- Muthumani P, Venkatraman S, Ramseshu KV, Meera R, Devi P, Kameswari B, et al. Pharmacological Studies of Anticancer, Anti Inflammatory Activities of *Murraya Koenigii* (Linn) Spreng in Experimental Animals. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Science and Research*. 2009;1(3):137-141.
- Ivander AS. Profil Tumor Necrosis Factor (TNF α) Berdasarkan Indeks Massa Tubuh (IMT) pada Mahasiswa Fakultas Kedokteran UNSRAT Angkatan 2014. *Jurnal e-Biomedik*. 2015;3(2):640-643.
- Lili I, Nusirwan A, Nuzulia I. Ekspresi Tumor Necrosis Faktor-Alfa (TNF α) dan Inter Leukin-10 (IL-10) pada Infeksi Malaria *Falciparum*. *Majalah Kedokteran Andalas*. 2008;1(32):16-28.
- Anisatu ZW. Review: Seledri (*Apium graveolens L.*): Botani, Ekologi, Fitokimia, Bioaktivitas dan Pemanfaatan. *Jurnal Pro-Life*. 2021;8(2):156-167.
- Yongkhamcha B. Biological Control of Dengue Fever Mosquitoes (*Aedes aegypti L.*) by Mintweed (*Hyptis suaveolens (L.) Poit*), Yam Bean (*Pachyrhizus erosus L.*), and Celery (*Apium graveolens L.*) Seed Extracts. *Suranaree University of Technology*. Thailand. 2010.
- Anisa L, Peni P, Melok AW. Daya Antibakteri Ekstrak Daun Seledri (*Apium graveolens L.*) terhadap *Porphyromonas gingivalis*. 2019;16(2):53-58.
- Komang DMB, Kadek NMD, Ni Kadek RP, Dwi MP, Putu RJKP, Luh PDY, Dewa AS. Uji Aktivitas Antiinflamasi Gel Ekstrak Kulit manggis dengan Variasi Konsentrasi. *Jurnal Ilmiah Medicamento*. 2020;6(2):89-93.
- Agustina, Miladiyah I. Uji Aktivitas Entiiinflamasi Ekstrak Etanol Daun Rambutan (*Nephelium lappaceum L.*) pada Tikus Putih (*Ratus norvegicus*) Jantan Galur Wistar. *Jurnal Kedokteran dan Kesehatan Indonesia*. 2013;5(1):47-58.
- Syari SS, Edwin Q, Olvie SD. Uji Aktivitas Antiinflamasi Ekstrak Etanol Daun Sesenawu (*Clerodendrum squamatum Vahl*) Terhadap Tikus Putih (*Rattus norvegicus L.*) yang Diinduksikan Karagenan. *Pharmacon*. 2021;10(3):025-1032.
- AOAC. Official Methods of Analysis, 17th edition. Association of Official Analytical Chemists, Maryland. 2010. USA.
- Nordan RP, Richards CD, Gaulide J. Measurement of Interleukin 6. *Current Protocols in Immunology*. 1996;6.6.1-6.6.5
- Valaperti A, Li Z, Eisenting MV, Müller EP. Diagnostic methods for the measurement of human TNF-alpha in clinical laboratory. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*. 2020;179:113010.
- Sun Y, Li M, Li X, Du J, Li W, Lin Y, Zhang Y, Wang Y, He W, Chen Q, Zhang Y, Wang X, Luo Y, Xiong A, Tang H. Characterization of volatile organic compounds in five celery (*Apium graveolens L.*) cultivars with different petiole colors by HS-SPME-GC-MS. *International Journal of Molecular Science*. 2023;24:13343. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms241713343>
- Chuhan F, Chen J, Lu J, Yi L, Tong X, Kang L, Pei S, Ouyang Y, Jiang L, Ding Y, Zhao X, Li S, Yang Y, Huang J, Zeng Q. Roles of Inflammation Factor in Melanogenesis (Review). *Molecular Medicine Reports*. 2020;21:1421-1430.
- Sylvia A, Setyaningrum T, Listiawan MY. Perbedaan Kadar Malondialdehid (MDA) sebagai Petanda Stres Oksidatif pada Berbagai Derajat Akne Vulgaris. *Berkala Ilmu Kesehatan Kulit dan Kelamin*. 2017;29(1):36-43.
- Kim SJ, Lee HJ, Kwon YH, Kim YC. Anti-inflammatory and skin barrier-repairing effects of kojic acid in lipopolysaccharide-treated human keratinocytes. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2017;18(2):353. doi: 10.3390/ijms1820353.
- Verma S, Singh A, Mishra A. Gallic acid: Molecular rival of cancer. *Environmental Toxicology and Pharmacology*. 2013;35(3):473-85. doi: 10.1016/j.etap.2013.01.004
- Yuan Z, Li L, Yao Y, Ji W, Zhang J, Liu H. Stachydrine ameliorateds LPS-induced inflammatory responses through suppressing the I κ B α /NF-kB and MAPKs signaling pathways in mouse mammary epithelial cells. *International Immunopharmacol*. 2017;50: 146-152. doi: 10.1016/j.intimp.2017.06.030
- Max X, Yan R, S. et al. Anti-inflammatory effects of polyphenol-enriched fraction from the leaves of celery (*Apium graveolens*) through modulating NF-kB and MAPK signaling pathways. *Journal of Functional Foods*. 2015;17:676-88. doi:10.1016/j.jff.2015.06.003.
- Hostetler G, R. K. T. Flavone deglycosylation increases their anti-infalmatory activity and absorption. *Mol Nutr Food Res*. 2012;56(4):558-69.
- Abugroun A, Gaznabi S, Natarajan A, Daoud H. Lime-induced phytophotodermatitis. *Oxf. Med. Case Rep*. 2019;470-472.
- Naghneh NS, Rafiei F, Shahbazi E, Gheisari MM. Variation of volatile compounds in celery through different vegetative stages. *Plant Physiology Reports*. 2023;28(3):476-480.